

**STUDY OF THE SYNTHESIS REACTION OF SUCCINIC ACID
LUPININ ETHER**

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The article is devoted to the synthesis of a new derivative of succinic acid with the natural alkaloid lupinin isolated from the plant *Anabasis aphylla* L. growing in the Aral Sea region, finding the optimal reaction conditions for the synthesis of succinic acid lupinin ether, identifying the physical and chemical constants of the synthesized compound and studying the prospects for its use in agriculture.

Keywords: synthesis, alkaloid, lupinin, succinic acid, *Anabasis aphylla* L.

Introduction. The alkaloid lupinin is a natural compound with a wide range of biological activity. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the synthesis of lupinin alkaloid derivatives, especially those containing organic acids, due to their potential use as pharmaceutical properties. The availability of lupinin and the presence of a simple alcohol group in the structure of the quinolizidine system, which makes it easy to obtain various derivatives of this alkaloid, is the reason for the search for active drugs among the derivatives of this alkaloid [1-5].

The purpose of the work. To synthesize a new derivative of succinic acid with the natural alkaloid lupinin, to find the optimal conditions for the reaction, to study the physical and chemical data and to establish the structure of the synthesized compound by spectroscopy data. The article will discuss the synthesis of the lupinin alkaloid ester with succinic acid, including the reaction mechanism and prospects for the biological activity of the resulting compound.

Results and discussion. Based on the literature data on the biological activity of alkaloid and succinic acid derivatives, it was interesting for us to synthesize an ester of succinic acid with a natural alkaloid lupinin isolated from the plant *Anabasis aphylla* L. growing in the Aral Sea region [6]. Because it has been shown that numerous derivatives of lupinin with organic acids have biologically active substances and are widely used in various sectors of the national economy, including agriculture as growth regulators, fungicides, herbicides and insecticides [1-5].

Succinic acid lupinin ether was obtained by esterification of lupinin with succinic acid in the presence of a sulfuric acid catalyst in xylene according to the following scheme:

To identify the optimal conditions for the reaction, we studied the reactions of the combination of lupinin with succinic acid in various molar ratios of reacting substances and the duration of the reaction. The results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Reaction conditions preparation of succinic acid lupinin ether

Initial reagents				Solvent	Reaction time (h)	Reaction temperature, (C°)	Reaction yield, (%)
Succinic acid		Lupinin					
G	mole	g	mole				
1,4	0,012	4.0	0.024	Toluene	12	108-111	31
-//-	-//-	-//-	-//-	-//-	18	-//-	37
-//-	-//-	-//-	-//-	-//-	24	-//-	48
-//-	-//-	-//-	-//-	-//-	30	-//-	57
-//-	-//-	-//-	-//-	-//-	35	-//-	51
-//-	-//-	-//-	-//-	-//-	39	-//-	46
0,7	0,006	2	0.012	Xylene	12	138-144	53
-//-	-//-	-//-	-//-	-//-	18	-//-	61
-//-	-//-	-//-	-//-	-//-	24	-//-	69
-//-	-//-	-//-	-//-	-//-	30	-//-	74
-//-	-//-	-//-	-//-	-//-	34	-//-	68
-//-	-//-	-//-	-//-	-//-	36	-//-	65

The table shows that the highest yield of succinic acid lupinin ether is observed when using succinic acid- lupinin in a molar ratio of 1:2 at a temperature of 138-144⁰C and a reaction duration of 30 hours.

The analysis of the obtained substance was analyzed by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) on the Agilent 1260 Infinity LC device. Structure of the substance it is proved that the molecular weight of the substance eluted through the column in 13.766 minutes coincides with the molecular weight of the ester of lupinin succinic acid by calculations.

Conclusions. A new lupinin ether of the lupinin alkaloid with succinic acid has been synthesized. The optimal conditions for the synthesis reaction were found, the physicochemical constants of the synthesized substance were identified and the structure was analyzed by HPLC.

The use of succinic acid lupinin ether in agriculture can lead to an increase in crop yields and quality, a reduction in the use of synthetic pesticides and a reduction in environmental impact.

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